

THE PRINCIPAL'S STRATEGY IN DEVELOPING EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES AT MTS TERPADU BERKAH PALANGKA RAYA

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Received: 01/04/2026 | Revised : 05/04/2026 | Accepted: 04/20/2026 | Published : 30/05/2026

Abstract

The strategy of the madrasah principal at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya in developing extracurricular activities with the main aim of fostering holistic student development, through extracurricular activities, it is necessary to make commitment efforts that consider the positive and negative impacts. This study aims to describe how the strategy for developing extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya. This study uses a descriptive qualitative method using data sources taken from three informants through in-depth interviews selected using *purposive sampling techniques*, the informants selected are the Madrasah Principal, Extracurricular Teacher, and Students participating in extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah. All interview results were then analyzed using data reduction techniques, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results of the analysis in this study are: 1) Extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah consist of 2 types of groups, namely 5 mandatory extracurriculars and 4 electives with a vision, mission and objectives that are closely related to the Qur'an. 2) The strategy for developing extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya consists of 3 steps, namely Strategy Formulation by forming a vision, mission and objectives. The principal uses SWOT analysis steps to find opportunities, threats, strengths and weaknesses. Followed by Strategy Implementation, namely forming an extracurricular organizational structure. Ending with Strategy Control in developing extracurricular activities at school, namely by setting standards, providing performance recognition, making work comparisons with work standards, and taking corrective actions that can be seen from weekly and monthly accountability reports, as well as attendance lists for each activity, both weekly and monthly.

Keywords: *Strategy, Extracurricular, Principal, Students.*

INTRODUCTION

Extracurricular activities are an important part that needs to be considered by the school because these activities are a forum for channeling and balancing the interests and talents of each student. Therefore, good management is needed from the school, especially the principal as a leader, in order to improve and balance student achievement in both academic and non-academic fields. Extracurricular activities have an important role to boost the increase in non-academic achievements such as recognizing children's abilities and talents to better recognize children's hobbies that lead to skills that the child has not yet recognized. Arifah (2024: 12) states that the principal and the board of teachers must strive to optimize the potential of all students by fostering abilities, talents, interests and paying attention to special needs in order to support extracurricular activities that take place at school.

In Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, it is stated that education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have spiritual religious strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals and skills needed by themselves, society, nation, and state (State Secretariat of the Republic of Indonesia, 2012). This law is also fully supported by regulations from the Minister of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia No. 39 of 2008 concerning Student Development, it is stated that Student Development aims to actualize students' potential in achieving superior achievements according to their talents and interests and is implemented through extracurricular and co-curricular activities (Ministry of National Education, 2008). The principal of Mts Terpadu Berkah explained that the strategy used by the madrasah principal is to encourage students to be more active and participate in extracurricular activities. According to the madrasah principal himself, extracurricular activities aim to foster student development holistically by instilling the ideals of character education. Social institutions, such as educational

institutions within the madrasah environment, play a crucial role in shaping the principles of student sociology. The madrasah principal recognizes the increasingly rapid progress in the current era of reform and communication, the school environment must dare to guarantee creativity to every student who will later be considered as madrasah alumni. Anticipating the impact of today's increasingly rapid scientific and technological breakthroughs through extracurricular activities requires a committed effort that considers both positive and negative impacts. Therefore, the madrasah principal created extracurricular activities as a facility to realize students' creative potential.

The principal stated that face-to-face learning or classroom teaching and learning activities are still considered insufficient to illustrate and foster opportunities for students to express their creativity openly and freely, resulting in only limited opportunities for the development of emotional and physical skills. The cognitive abilities developed are usually centered on understanding academic content, information retention, and logical thinking. As a result, educational achievement is often evaluated solely on students' ability to respond to factual questions, neglecting the development of their creative abilities. To achieve all of this, the principal needs a good strategy. In developing extracurricular activities, the principal has three important stages: strategy formulation, strategy implementation, and strategy control.

MTs Terpadu Berkah, which is essentially an independent institution because in improving facilities and infrastructure and also financing extracurricular activities, the principal does not rely entirely on the foundation, where the principal utilizes and manages funds optimally. Extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah can also be said to be upgraded, or it could be said that even though MTs Terpadu Berkah is a private institution, the principal can keep up with other public schools. Extracurricular activities are indeed essential in schools. Besides enhancing and recognizing student talents, they also help increase student interest in learning and academic achievement. Therefore, this research is highly needed, and the method used is deemed to be helpful and supportive of the research's sustainability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As with the research conducted by Fida Mawaddah (2023) regarding "The Principal's Strategy in Improving Students' Non-Academic Achievement Through Extracurricular Activities at MTS Negeri 3 Medan", the results of the study show that at MTs Negeri 3 Medan not only focus on performance academic just, but Non-academic achievement Students' academic achievement can be seen from their learning outcomes, where none of the results fall below the KKM (Minimum Completion Criteria) score. Meanwhile, other achievements can be seen from various activities to develop students' academic achievement. skills, potential, interest, And talent for his students as well as increase performance Students through extracurricular activities win various competitions both between schools and as representatives from a region to participate in national competitions. Research conducted by Achmad Fahrizal Zulfani (2014) regarding "Implementation of Extracurricular Management for Increase Performance Student Non-Academic in SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL Al-Multazam Mojokerto", the strategies implemented include planning extracurricular activities, implementing extracurricular activity programs, and evaluation, which includes an end-of-year report submitted to the principal.

Nur Achmadi's (2021) research states that thanks to the charismatic leadership of the Madrasah Principal and his focus on achieving the school's vision, mission, and goals by transforming the vision, mission, and goals of the Madrasah into tangible work that we can understand so that what is desired in the vision, mission, and goals can be achieved. This phenomenon is certainly interesting to study, whether this condition is related to the type, style, and leadership model of the Madrasah Principal in managing MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Timur. Thus, the researcher is interested in conducting a thesis-based research with the title "Leadership of the Principal of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri 1 Kotawaringin Timur."

Muchamad Arif N (2018) stated in his research, MA Al Khoiriyyah Semarang has often been a champion in various competitions at the Regency/City level of Semarang and has become a representative to the Provincial level, among the student achievements are MTQ, and Pancak Silat. Extracurricular activities held at MA Al Khoiriyyah Semarang include, scouts, silat hisbullah, qiroah tilawatil Qur'an, BBC, wall magazine, fudsal and modern rebana. This research will be conducted at MA Al Khoiriyyah Semarang which discusses how to implement Extracurricular Activity Management to Develop Interests and Talents so that it can produce outstanding students in various inter-school competitions. Asrizal (2018) stated in his research that extracurricular activities at SMAN 1 Bandar Dua, Pidie Jaya Regency, can be seen from several aspects, namely from the extracurricular objectives emphasizing the distribution and cultivation of individual talents or potential through intensive activities, from student involvement, that extracurricular activities must be taken by each student based on their own needs and from the perspective of the activities carried out, extracurricular programs can include various activities that attract students. Thus, the

development of extracurricular activities in schools requires good management and coaching actions so that these activities are truly beneficial for students. Previous research can be used as a reference in future research so that there are several descriptions of strategies that must be carried out by the principal in developing activities at school, especially extracurricular activities.

Strategy Theory

According to Fattah and Ali (2007: 6.32), as quoted by Yusuf Hadijaya, strategy is the art of using an organization's capabilities and resources to achieve its goals through effective relationships with the environment under the most favorable conditions. Thus, strategy is the basic framework within which an organization continues its life by adapting to its environment. According to Johnson and schools (2016:29) strategy is the direction and scope of an organization in the long term that achieves benefits for the organization through the configuration of resources in a challenging environment to meet market needs and fulfill stakeholder expectations. Strategy generates and will direct the organization on what, why, Who Which responsible answer, How many cost, How many long, And what results are to be achieved. This allows the organization to predict, prepare, implement, and evaluate activities/events that will occur. Thus, every activity in every step need existence determination as reference in its operation.

Principal Strategy Theory

Etymologically, a principal is the equivalent of a *school principal*, whose goal is to carry out *principalship* or school leadership. The term "principal" refers to everything related to the principal's primary duties and functions. Besides principal, other terms include school administration, school leader, school manager, and so on (Hasan Basri, 2014: 39). As a leader, the principal has a significant influence in improving the quality of learning outcomes and bears the responsibility for ensuring the school's success in achieving its educational goals. According to William, the principal's role as an educational leader is focused on helping achieve educational goals. Therefore, the principal is responsible for overseeing and evaluating the work of teachers at the school. Therefore, the principal needs to use strategies to ensure progress within the school itself, both improving teacher performance and student achievement, both academic and non-academic, in order to achieve the school's vision, mission, and goals.

Principal strategy refers to a specific approach or methodology used by the principal to effectively achieve established goals with the aim of reducing failure. Strategy refers to top management planning to achieve results aligned with an organization's vision, mission, and objectives (Bagus Eko Dono, 2021 : 15).

The strategy can be divided into 3 stages, namely as follows.

1. Strategy Formulation

Strategy formulation involves creating a comprehensive plan for efficient management based on environmental analysis. This includes the formulation of a vision, mission, and objectives, as well as the creation of strategies and policy guidelines. Strategy formulation involves the process of identifying and planning specific actions necessary to achieve objectives. To develop strategies effectively, relying on environmental analysis is crucial. This process involves collecting accurate and comprehensive data and information from an examination of the surrounding environment. Based on the above description, Fred R. David and Forest R. David concluded that the indicators of strategy formulation are as follows (Fred R. David & Forest R. David, 2015: 8).

a. Vision, Mission and Goals

Vision refers to a cognitive representation of a future state constructed using logical assumptions and reasonable assumptions about what lies ahead. This mental model is shaped by our own perspective and centers on something important, which is then defined. Vision is a conceptual framework that can be actualized by individuals and organizations through their engagement and behavior (Nur Fitriyani, 2021: 147).

A mission is a broad and comprehensive statement that outlines the overall aims and objectives. It also represents the steps or stages a company, agency, or organization must go through to achieve its primary vision (Misda Sari, 2020: 26).

b. SWOT Analysis

David Hunger and Thomas L. Wheelen define strategy as a series of managerial choices and activities that ultimately shape a company's long-term performance. The initial stage of strategy formulation involves identifying and analyzing all aspects that could potentially influence the achievement of objectives, including the application of a SWOT analysis. The authors state that "SWOT analysis is the methodical

identification of institutional factors used to develop a company's strategy." This analysis is based on a logical approach that aims to optimize strengths and opportunities while minimizing weaknesses and threats. SWOT analysis is a method used to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of a particular situation or entity (Asep Effendi et al., 2018: 28).

1) Opportunity

Opportunities are positive external situations and factors that help the organization achieve or exceed its vision and mission. Within opportunities, we need to look for characteristics related to opportunities in the surrounding environment or related sectors that exist for the institution, thereby encouraging the institution to progress.

2) Threat

Threats present significant obstacles to an organization's current or desired status, which can result in the organization failing to achieve its vision and mission.

3) Strength

Strengths refer to the resources, skills, and other advantages possessed. Student enthusiasm is the driving force behind the implementation of extracurricular activities.

4) Weakness

Weaknesses refer to constraints or weaknesses in resources, talent, and determination that consistently hinder the operations of an organization.

2. Strategy Implementation

This stage represents the implementation of the formulated strategy. Currently, this involves multiple stakeholders and requires collaboration across different departments within the company. Parties or work groups, particularly those at the management level responsible for implementing the strategy, must understand its essence and maintain a consistent interpretation. This implementation is the action of the established strategy formulation, aimed at ensuring that the formulated strategy can be implemented effectively and truly achieve the predetermined goals or direction (Nur Kholis, 2014: 153).

It's important to note that a well-formulated plan doesn't automatically guarantee successful implementation. This depends on the company or institution's dedication and commitment to its implementation. Based on the description above, the author can conclude that the signs of strategy implementation are as follows (Hasan Basri, 2014: 11).

a. Organizational Structure Analysis

Organizational structure shows the arrangement and framework of the embodiment of a fixed pattern of relationships between functions, positions, sections, or people that indicate different positions, responsibilities and authority tasks in an organization.

b. Organizational/School Culture Analysis

Organizational culture is a determining factor in the successful implementation of a strategy within an organization, while other businesses with similar circumstances may struggle to adopt the same strategy. School culture refers to the school's background, encompassing its values, customs, traditions, and rituals. This culture is developed over a significant period of time through the collective efforts of all members of the school community. School culture has a significant impact on the school community and their levels of motivation and enjoyment. In the context of functional schools, the term "school culture" is typically used to describe the overall atmosphere of the school, encompassing the collective thinking and behavior of the school community.

c. Leadership Style Analysis

Leadership is a characteristic of a leader, meaning the elements inherent in a leader in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, as well as realizing their vision and mission in leading subordinates, the community in a social environment, organization, or country. Thus, the meaning of leadership is applicable and realistic. Leadership is the power and effort exerted by someone, who serves as a leader, in influencing others to carry out a predetermined work plan in order to achieve goals effectively and efficiently.

According to Edward Sallis, certain leadership styles in educational settings have the potential to initiate significant improvements in the quality of the institution. Studies on principal effectiveness show that a school's success is directly related to the success of its principal. Principals are individuals who have optimistic expectations for staff, teachers, and students. Therefore, when adopting strategies, it is important to analyze leadership styles to facilitate the achievement of the school's organizational goals.

3. Strategic Control

Strategic control is all the methods and analyses used to monitor, evaluate, and modify strategies in adjusting the activities of an organization or institution to the needs for survival caused by constantly changing external forces, in order to achieve goals. Based on the arguments above, the researcher concludes that the indications of strategic control are as follows (Nur Kholis, 2014: 139).

a. Establishing Standards and Methods for Measuring Work Performance

The standards in question are basic benchmarks for work performance, specifically points selected throughout the program that assess work performance. These points serve as indicators for managers of progress within the organization, eliminating the need to closely monitor each step of the plan's implementation.

b. Performance Measurement

The next step involves assessing or evaluating work performance against pre-established benchmarks. While this isn't always feasible, the ideal approach is to proactively measure work performance against standards.

This allows for the identification of any deviations from standards before they occur. If you don't have the necessary talent, it's crucial to detect any discrepancies as soon as possible.

c. Performing Performance Comparisons with Standards

After the two previous procedures have been completed, the next step is to compare the measurement results with the predetermined targets or standards. Managers will assess that everything is being managed effectively if performance meets the established criteria.

d. Taking Corrective Action

The control process is considered incomplete unless action is taken to correct any deviations that may arise. By aligning standards with the organizational structure and measuring work performance against those standards, the process of addressing negative deviations can be accelerated. This is because managers already have a clear understanding of which aspects of implementation are being addressed.

Extracurricular Theory

Extracurricular activities refer to additional activities that are not part of the formal curriculum and are usually optional. These extracurricular activities are designed to provide students with additional opportunities to engage in positive and enriching activities outside of regular classroom hours. The goal is to help students expand their knowledge and skills, develop their talents and interests, and foster their creativity. Through various activities, students are encouraged to develop and enhance their abilities and skills (Nur Hamdiyati, 2023: 50).

In general, it can be said that extracurricular activities are activities carried out outside of school hours organized by the school that are designed to develop students' skills, interests, and talents. The main purpose and role of extracurricular activities is to encourage students' holistic development, encompassing emotional, intellectual, and physical aspects. These activities aim to cultivate students' hidden talents and interests, increase their capacity to interact with their surroundings, and improve their communication skills, while still upholding the principles of justice and equality.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative descriptive research method with a documentation, observation, and interview approach in data collection. Data sources were taken from three informants through in-depth interviews selected using a *purposive sampling technique*. The selected informants have met four criteria: understanding the problem being studied, having the time to provide information, and providing information according to the facts that occur in the field. After the interviews were completed, the author conducted a transcription process, then the author collected data according to research needs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Education is a means used to develop personal abilities in order to form generations who are faithful, pious, have noble morals, are knowledgeable, capable, creative and live independently. To form and achieve all of this, it is necessary to establish a structured and directed learning program in a curriculum or learning program both academic and non-academic, so that extracurricular activities are needed that can help support the continuity of student learning at school both inside and outside the classroom to help increase this confidence, recognize interests and talents and know themselves. The learning objectives of the school are stated in the vision, mission and objectives

of the school itself. Each school has a vision, mission and objectives for its establishment to be a benchmark for every development and progress in the school itself and the quality of the alumni formed. One of them is MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya. MTs Terpadu Berkah has a vision, mission, and goals that are appropriate and in line with the development of children's character in this era of rapid globalization. One of these is a learning system that utilizes the Quran as the primary guideline in daily life. To realize the school's vision, mission, and goals, the principal took action by establishing extracurricular activities with a strategy of formation as early as possible. The findings of this study are as follows.

Extracurricular Activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

Extracurricular activities are part of school activities that help students identify their hobbies, interests, and talents. Indirectly, extracurricular activities serve as a place or forum facilitated by the school to help students identify and hone their abilities. According to Masnawati, Darmawan, and Masfufah (2023: 310), in addition to helping students hone and channel their interests and talents, participating in extracurricular activities has several benefits, such as:

- a. Training responsibility and independence
- b. A place to hone talents and interests
- c. A means to learn to organize and socialize
- d. Training cooperation
- e. Cultivate discipline and commitment.

Each school has a Vision, Mission and goals that are almost the same in holding extracurricular activities, one of which is MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya which is a private school under the auspices of the Barokah Foundation on JL. G Obos Induk KM. 5,5 No. 51, Menteng Village, Jekan Raya District, Palangka Raya City, Central Kalimantan.

MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya has a Vision of "Creating a Generation of Noble and Achieving Quran Memorizers" with a Mission of "Organizing Quran education. Extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya have the goal and function of being a place to develop students' potential, build student character, improve student skills, and channel positive student energy. In addition, the goal and function of extracurricular activities are also to improve students' non-academic skills, become a refreshing place to achieve the vision, mission and main goals, and teach students independence. Extracurricular activities can also create a generation that is more characterful and superior. According to Sukron Alamsyah, Muslimah and Rio Irawan in their research (2024: 289) stated that in the context of character formation of students, research findings prove that the manifested discipline character includes three main aspects, namely; time discipline, worship discipline and discipline in enforcing rules. Time discipline is reflected in students' compliance with punctual arrival to school, entering class, worship discipline is reflected in students being punctual in worship (Duha and Dzuhur prayers). Meanwhile, discipline in enforcing rules includes students' compliance with school regulations, such as wearing uniforms according to regulations and adhering to applicable rules. This demonstrates that the three characteristics above play a crucial role in the principles used at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya in conducting extracurricular activities. The principle of extracurricular activities is individual, where students must choose according to their own potential and talents, as well as the principle of choice that is tailored to their own desires. Some extracurricular activities in schools are divided into two parts: mandatory extracurricular activities and elective extracurricular activities, as follows.

No	Mandatory Extracurriculars	Optional Extracurriculars
1	Dhuha Prayer in Congregation	Calligraphy
2	Recitation of Asmaul Husana	Dance
3	Murotal	Futsal
4	Tahfiz	Habsy
5	Scout	

Strategy for Developing Extracurricular Activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

- a. Strategy Formulation

The primary element of strategy formulation is the existence of a vision, mission, goals, and objectives for the activity itself. Strategy formulation involves creating a comprehensive plan for efficient management based on environmental analysis. This includes the formulation of a mission, vision, and objectives, as well as the creation of strategies and policy guidelines (M. Nasir, 2024: 6). Strategy formulation involves the process of

identifying and planning specific actions necessary to achieve goals. The Vision of the establishment of extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya is "To create a platform for developing the potential of superior, character-based, innovative, and noble students" with the Mission of "developing talents and interests, character building, achieving achievements and emotional balance". Meanwhile, the purpose of establishing extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah is "to channel students' talents and interests and increase students' self-confidence".

In today's era of globalization, and with the advancement of technology, character education is essential and must be instilled in children to prevent them from being swept away by the increasingly Western (free) social environment. To address this, the principal has implemented extracurricular activities at school. In addition to keeping students busy, these activities also help them develop themselves and recognize the character traits taught by the school through extracurricular activities such as discipline taught in scouting, regular congregational Dhuha prayers, and timely memorization (Tahfiz) of the Koran.

In addition, extracurricular activities can be used as a forum for students to recognize their own talents and abilities that must be honed and mastered so that potential is not lost. For this reason, the principal uses a good strategy in developing extracurricular activities in the school he leads. The principal uses a SWOT analysis as a tool that can help analyze various factors systematically to maximize the sustainability of extracurricular activities at MTs Terpaapadu Berkah Palangka Raya. Asep Effendi, et al (2018: 28) stated that SWOT analysis is a methodical identification of *institutional factors* used to develop company strategies, this analysis is based on a logical approach that aims to optimize strengths and opportunities while minimizing weaknesses and dangers. SWOT analysis is also a method used to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of a particular situation or entity. The results of the SWOT analysis conducted by the Principal of MTs Terpaapadu Berkah Palangka Raya are as follows.

- 1) *Strength*
 - a) Targeted allocation of school funds
 - b) The motivational boost from the teacher is very big
 - c) The students' great enthusiasm in participating
 - d) Adequate supporting facilities and infrastructure
- 2) *Weaknesses*
 - a) Poor time management
 - b) Often clashes with activities carried out by the foundation
 - c) Lack of consistency from coaches/cooperation is still in the planning category
- 3) *Opportunity*
 - a) Technological advances that help make it easier for students to explore
 - b) The potential of students varies greatly
- 4) *Threat*
 - a) Instant culture that influences students' enthusiasm for learning
 - b) Gadget addiction where students prefer to play with their cellphones rather than practice on the field.

The principal's strategy formulation in developing extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya is based on the theory presented by Fred R David, Forest R David, namely strategy formulation *includes* developing a vision and mission, identifying external opportunities and threats of the organization, determining strengths and weaknesses, creating long-term goals (Fred R. David and Forest R. David. 2015: 4), namely having a vision of realizing a generation of memorizers of the Qur'an who have noble character and achieve, so that the extracurricular activities that are required for students are congregational Dhuha Prayer, Tahfiz, and scouts to train discipline, hone memorization skills and assisted with reading Asmaul Husna before starting learning and murotal to create an Islamic learning environment. While the mission at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya is to create a conducive, Islamic learning environment and support the development of student character, improve academic and non-academic quality to encourage student learning achievement as a whole, and develop student potential through religion, art and sports in a balanced manner. So the principal formed extracurricular activities that were optional, such as calligraphy, dance, futsal and habsy.

With the existence of quite good strength findings, with the allocation of funds that are right on target, the existence of encouragement or motivation from teachers is very large, facilities and infrastructure that support and enthusiasm of students in participating in extracurricular activities are utilized by the principal to be the main source of needs analysis in forming extracurricular activities that are of interest to students. Some extracurricular activities that are very popular with students are futsal, habsy and dance, apart from being

hobbies and interests of the students themselves, the enthusiasm of other students who are not too interested is an attraction to create good opportunities in preparing the right strategy formulation. According to Zakiyah and Munawaroh (2018: 44) stated that the enthusiasm of students is the strength of the implementation of extracurricular activities. The existence of technological advances and the very varied potential of students will further increase the progress and skills of the students themselves so that new talents emerge that hone students' self-confidence. However, anticipation is needed due to the lack of extracurricular development at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya, namely poor time management due to frequent clashes with activities carried out by the foundation impromptu and the lack of consistent training time from the coaches themselves, especially coaches taken from outside the school, this is influenced by cooperation that is still in the planning category (a less strong MoU). This will give rise to several internal factors due to the threat of instant culture that will affect children's enthusiasm for learning in the field, the existence of gadget addiction that makes students prefer playing with cellphones and staying in front of the TV screen rather than practicing directly in the field. The need for anticipation and discipline is very much needed in this extracurricular activity development program.

Once it is felt that the strategy formulation is well-organized and appropriate, the next step is the need for implementation of the strategy used for the development process of the extracurricular program at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya.

b. Strategy Implementation

Strategy implementation is the stage of carrying out the formulated strategy. This implementation is the action of the established strategy formulation, aimed at ensuring that the formulated strategy can be implemented properly and truly achieve the predetermined goals or direction (Nur Kholis, 2014: 153).

The implementation of the strategy itself is divided into several scopes as follows.

1) Organizational Structure at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

Organizational structure shows the arrangement of the framework for the embodiment of a fixed pattern of relationships between functions, positions, sections, or people that show different positions, responsibilities, and authority tasks in an organization (Bisri Mustofa, 2010: 103).

The organizational structure at MTS Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya is with the Principal himself as the person in charge, with the Deputy Principal as the coordinator for Student Affairs and several class teachers and supervisors who are invited from outside according to their respective potentials.

2) Organizational Culture at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

Organizational culture is a determining factor in the successful implementation of a strategy within an organization. Meanwhile, school culture refers to the school's background, encompassing its values, customs, traditions, and rituals (Ismayanti, Rahmah, Fathi, Jamaliyah, Rahmadani, and Arfinanti, 2020: 120). In the context of functional schools, the term school culture is typically used to describe the overall school atmosphere, encompassing collective thinking and behavior, and school communication (Djoko Hartomo, 2021: 38).

Likewise, the organizational culture at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya. Based on field research, the organizational culture instilled at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya requires a combination of good cooperation between teachers and transparency in organizational management within the school. Furthermore, each extracurricular activity is not differentiated from the others so that they support each other and are not biased. Most students choose to explore knowledge, so some students participate in more than one extracurricular activity. This is considered not a problem because there is no difference between one extracurricular activity and another, only the learning and knowledge received are adjusted to the activities in each type of extracurricular.

3) The Principal's Leadership Style at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

According to Edwan Sallis in Hasan Basri's book (2014: 11), certain leadership styles in educational settings have the potential to initiate significant improvements in the quality of institutions. Studies on the effectiveness of principals show that the success of a school is directly related to the success of its principal. When adopting a strategy, it is important to analyze leadership styles to facilitate the achievement of organizational goals in schools, one of which is MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya. This opinion is in line with Sonedi, Tutut Sholihah, and Sihasbi in their research (2018: 19) that a madrasah principal must have skills not only in the field of administration, but also must have the ability to lead, organize, be able to motivate and encourage teachers, educational staff, and students to study harder, so that students can achieve good achievements and the success of the madrasah will also increase rapidly. This is very

necessary because the principal is the main person responsible for every activity that takes place in the school.

Iis Aisul Istianah, Ahmadi, and Siminto (2025: 36) stated in their research that the principal is responsible for achieving educational goals by motivating subordinates toward achieving the stated educational goals. In this case, the principal is tasked with carrying out leadership functions, both those related to achieving educational goals and creating a school climate and culture that is conducive to the implementation of a productive, effective, and efficient learning process.

Based on the results of field research, according to the principal and vice principal of student affairs, leadership style in the educational environment has the potential to initiate significant improvements in the quality of the institution. A good principal is not only good at giving orders but also must go directly to the field to provide support to teachers. The principal at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya prioritizes high tolerance, always coordinates in every activity, listens to and supports positive ideas from teachers, protects and makes good contributions, and provides support and backup *by* accompanying and finding solutions as soon as possible. This is done by the principal to anticipate delays in resolving problems so that solutions must be found immediately to prevent them from spreading and getting bigger. According to Khaeril Anwar, Fahmi, Ahmadi and Muslimah (2021: 366), the leadership style of the madrasah principal is democratic as evidenced by activities that are collaborative in nature, so they are held in meetings with teachers to reach mutual agreement, visionary, proven by implementing work programs in accordance with the vision and mission, conditional, proven by consistency and making appropriate policies that are in accordance with needs.

c. Strategic Control

Strategic control is widely used in the analysis process. This method is used to monitor, evaluate, and modify strategies to align an organization's or institution's activities with the need for survival and to achieve goals (Nur Kholis, 2014: 139). The steps in drawing conclusions in strategic control indications are as follows.

1) Establishing Standards and Methods for Measuring Work Achievement or Performance at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

The standards in question are basic benchmarks for work performance, specifically points selected throughout the program that assess work performance. These points serve as indicators for managers of progress within the organization, eliminating the need to closely monitor each step of plan implementation (Ismail Yusanto, 2020: 144).

Based on the results of field research, the Deputy Head of Student Affairs and the Principal of MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya set the work performance standards for teachers who manage extracurricular activities as seen from the attendance of trainers and students of at least 80% at each meeting, the extracurricular agenda that is implemented must also be at least 90% and there must be at least one extracurricular student who achieves achievements in competitions.

The percentage of attendance is considered to greatly influence the determination of standards and methods for measuring this achievement because each meeting will certainly provide new learning or material that is received as well as consistency of teaching so that the resulting generation will also improve and be able to compete with other schools both outside and within the region (sub-district, district, provincial and national levels).

2) Measuring Work Performance in Extracurricular Activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

According to the Principal and Deputy Principal for Student Affairs at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya, performance can be measured by the number of achievements or competition results students have won, whether trophies, medals, or other awards. Teacher performance, on the other hand, can be measured by the achievement of plans and the realization of reports.

To measure the work performance of teachers who manage extracurricular activities, it is done monthly and then quarterly, based on the achievement of planning and based on the realization of reports.

3) Comparison of Work Performance with Work Standards at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

Based on interviews, observations, and documentation on comparing work performance with standards in the development of extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya, the principal held meetings with all deputy principals to review the extracurricular activities that had been implemented and any obstacles encountered. The meetings were held once a month before meetings with all teachers and staff.

To compare work performance with the work standards for extracurricular implementation, this is seen through the evaluation process to what extent the program has been achieved, activity reports, and student and supervisor attendance lists.

4) **Corrective Action Taking at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya**

The control process is considered incomplete unless action is taken to correct any deviations that may arise. By aligning standards with the organizational structure and measuring work performance against those standards, the process of addressing negative deviations can be accelerated. This is because managers already have a clear understanding of which aspects of the implementation process are most effective. tasks by individuals or work groups that require corrective action (Nur Kholis, 2014: 140).

To take corrective action in extracurricular activities, adjustments are made to the collected data in the form of weekly and monthly reports and evaluations are carried out as soon as possible.

CONCLUSION

Based on the description of the results and discussion above, it can be concluded that:

1. Extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya consist of 2 types of categories, namely mandatory and elective extracurricular activities, which consist of:

No	Mandatory Extracurriculars	Optional Extracurriculars
1	Dhuha Prayer in Congregation	Calligraphy
2	Recitation of Asmaul Husana	Dance
3	Murotal	Futsal
4	Tahfiz	Habsy
5	Scout	

By classifying mandatory and optional extracurricular activities, it is in accordance with the vision, mission, and goals of the school and the formation of extracurricular activities is to achieve the vision, mission and goals of the madrasah to create a generation of memorizers who have noble morals and achieve and create a learning environment that is not far from Al-Qur'an education, Islamic and directed discipline, and helps hone students' self-confidence, improve academic and non-academic quality in order to encourage students' achievements and potential through religion, art and sports.

2. The strategy for developing extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya uses 3 steps, namely:

a. Strategy Formulation seen from:

- 1) Vision, Mission, Goals and Targets of Extracurricular Activities

The principal's strategy formulation in developing extracurricular activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya, namely strategy formulation , includes developing a vision and mission, identifying external opportunities and threats to the organization, determining strengths and weaknesses, creating long-term goals.

b. Strategy Implementation

The implementation of the strategy itself is divided into several parts, namely

- 1) The organizational structure of the Integrated MTs Berkah Palangka Raya

The organizational structure at MTS Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya is with the Principal himself as the person in charge, with the Deputy Principal as the coordinator for Student Affairs and several class teachers and supervisors who are invited from outside according to their respective potentials.

- 2) The organizational culture of MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

The organizational culture instilled in MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya is that there must be good combination and cooperation between teachers as well as transparency in organizational management at the school.

- 3) Leadership style of the principal of MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya

The leadership style of the Principal at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya prioritizes high tolerance, always coordinates in every activity, listens to and supports positive ideas from teachers, protects and provides good contributions, and provides support and accompaniment and seeks solutions as soon as possible.

c. Strategic Control

The strategic controls carried out are as follows:

- 1) Establishing Standards and Methods for Measuring Work Achievement or Performance at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya
The standard of work performance of teachers who manage extracurricular activities is seen from the presence of coaches and students of at least 80% at each meeting, the extracurricular agenda that is implemented must also be at least 90% and there must be at least one extracurricular student who achieves an achievement in the competition.
- 2) Measuring Work Performance in Extracurricular Activities at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya
Performance measurement can be seen from the number of achievements or competition results students have won, whether in the form of trophies, medals, or other awards. Meanwhile, teacher performance can be seen from the achievement of plans and the realization of reports.
- 3) Comparison of Work Performance with Work Standards at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya
To compare work performance with the work standards for extracurricular implementation, this is seen through the evaluation process to what extent the program has been achieved, activity reports, and student and supervisor attendance lists.
- 4) Corrective Action Taking at MTs Terpadu Berkah Palangka Raya
To take corrective action in extracurricular activities, adjustments are made to the collected data in the form of weekly and monthly reports and evaluations are carried out as soon as possible.

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